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**An Investigation into the Accuracy and
Efficiency of
Distributed Real-Time Cost
Attribution Architectures
for Multi-Tenant LLM Inference
Systems**

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Abstract

SaaS products that embed Large Language Model features face a recurring operational problem: working out, in near-real-time, what each tenant actually costs in inference. Provider invoices arrive hours to days after the API call and rarely match the call-time estimate, because of batch discounts, rate-limit surcharges and pricing variance. This is, at its core, an eventual-consistency problem between two derived views.

This dissertation implements and empirically compares three distributed architectures for the problem (Event Sourcing with CQRS, Streaming Aggregation backed by Apache Kafka, and Batch Reconciliation) behind a single common interface, driven by an identical seeded synthetic workload, and evaluated on five quantitative metrics across twenty-nine runs covering baseline, batch-ingestion, stress, and reproducibility scenarios. All twenty-nine runs completed without failure on a single host running PostgreSQL and Kafka in containers.

The principal finding is that no single architecture is dominant. At the 10 000-event baseline, with three measurement replicates per cell and 95% bootstrap confidence intervals, Batch Reconciliation sustains the highest ingestion throughput (1 822 events/s, p_{95} ingest latency 0.57 ms) but the slowest reconciliation latency (57 ms p_{95}). Streaming Aggregation and Event Sourcing with CQRS sit close together at ingestion (606 and 527 events/s respectively, p_{95} around 2.2–2.5 ms) but separate sharply at reconciliation: Streaming is the fastest (1.2 ms p_{95}) and Event Sourcing the intermediate (4.2 ms p_{95}). Event Sourcing uniquely preserves a complete audit trail of cost events, a property the other two architectures discard by construction. Attribution accuracy is identical across the three engines, which falls out of the methodology rather than reflecting any architectural property. Reproducibility was demonstrated empirically across three seeds with three replicates each: throughput coefficient of variation across seeds remains under 6% for every architecture, and the relative architecture ordering is preserved at every seed.

The result is a workload-conditional recommendation: Batch for ingestion-heavy workloads with infrequent reconciliation, Streaming for reconciliation-heavy workloads, Event Sourcing for balanced workloads or where the immutable event log is itself a requirement.

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Glossary

Term	Definition
Attribution accuracy	The percentage deviation between an architecture's running estimate of cost for a given window and the simulated provider invoice for that window.
Box-Muller transform	A method for sampling from a Gaussian distribution by combining two uniformly distributed random numbers. The workload generator uses it to produce realistic token-count distributions.
Convergence lag	The wall-clock time between the close of an invoice period and the moment the invoice's reconciliation timestamp is written by the simulator.
CQRS	Command Query Responsibility Segregation. An architectural pattern in which the data model used to update state (commands) is kept separate from the model used to read state (queries).
Eventual consistency	A consistency model where derived views are not guaranteed to agree at all times but converge to the same value once all updates have propagated.
Event sourcing	A pattern in which every change to application state is stored as an immutable event in a durable, append-only log. The current state is derived by replaying or projecting those events.
FinOps	A discipline combining financial accountability with cloud operations practice, promoted by the FinOps Foundation, with the FOCUS specification as its open data model.
KRaft	Kafka's mode of operation in which the cluster's metadata is managed by a Raft-based controller quorum, removing the historical dependency on Apache ZooKeeper.
Mulberry32	A 32-bit-state pseudo-random number generator widely used in simulation work, chosen here for the deterministic reproducibility of seeded runs.
p50, p95, p99	The 50th, 95th and 99th percentiles of a measured distribution. The report uses these in place of arithmetic means because tail behaviour, not the average, determines user-visible performance.
Reconciliation	The process of comparing an architecture's running cost estimate against the actual provider invoice for the same window and computing the deviation.

Term	Definition
Tumbling window	A non-overlapping, fixed-duration window used by the streaming aggregator to bucket events for aggregation. The default in this implementation is one hour.
UsageEvent	The immutable record produced by the SDK or workload generator for each LLM call. Carries provider, model, token counts, estimated cost, latency, attribution metadata, and timestamp.

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

SaaS products are embedding LLM features faster than the infrastructure around them has caught up. A single user interaction can fan out to several models from several providers, each charged by token rather than by call, at rates that vary by model, by operation type, by cache hit status, and increasingly by plan tier. The bill, when it arrives, is the sum of those per-call charges over the tenant's activity in a given hour or day, plus or minus whatever batch discount, rate-limit surcharge or retroactive pricing change the provider applies at settlement time. It almost never matches the figure that was computed at call time, and it almost always shows up hours or days after the calls themselves.

A SaaS provider that needs to know what each tenant cost in near-real-time, whether to compute margin, enforce per-customer budgets, or power an operator dashboard, is now in the awkward position of reconciling two views of the same cost: a running estimate computed at call time, and an invoice that lands later. Reconciliation here is an eventual-consistency problem, and the architecture that does the reconciling has direct consequences for ingestion throughput, query latency, reconciliation latency, audit properties, and how operationally complex the whole thing is to run.

1.2 Research Questions

The investigation is guided by three research questions:

1. **Accuracy.** How closely can each architecture reconcile real-time cost estimates (based on token counts and published pricing) with the actual provider invoices, and how does the accuracy change over time as reconciliation events arrive?
2. **Efficiency.** What are the latency and throughput characteristics of each architecture when it is processing cost attribution events at scale, with multiple tenants sending requests at the same time?
3. **Architecture suitability.** Under what workload conditions (tenant count, request volume, billing delay) does each architecture perform best, and what trade-offs does each carry?

The three architectural approaches under investigation are Event Sourcing with Command Query Responsibility Segregation (CQRS), Streaming Aggregation backed by Apache Kafka, and Batch Reconciliation. All three are implemented behind the same component contract, driven by the same seeded synthetic workload, and evaluated on the same five quantitative metrics: attribution accuracy, latency at p50, p95 and p99, throughput, convergence lag, and resource efficiency.

1.3 Contributions

The work makes four contributions to the research and engineering literature on multi-tenant cost attribution.

The first is a like-for-like comparison of the three architectures in the specific context of LLM cost attribution. Each architecture has been treated separately in the existing literature, and LLM serving has been studied separately again, but the three approaches have not previously been put through controlled experiments under the demands of token-priced, delayed-invoice billing.

The second is a seeded synthetic workload methodology, implemented in TypeScript using the Mulberry32 pseudo-random number generator and Box-Muller sampling. The same seed produces the same sequence of events, the same model selections, and the same token counts on every run, so the three architectures are fed byte-identical input on each measurement. Reproducibility is demonstrated empirically by re-running identical specifications across three seeds and measuring the resulting variance.

The third is the implementation itself: a six-package pnpm workspace, a Docker Compose stack with PostgreSQL and Apache Kafka, a benchmark runner that writes both CSV and JSON, an experiment sweep script that drives the full matrix in one command, and a Python plot-generation pipeline that emits the figures embedded throughout Chapter 5. Reproducibility instructions in Appendix E take a clean checkout to a finished PDF in three commands.

The fourth contribution is a workload-conditional architectural recommendation for SaaS teams building cost-attribution pipelines. Rather than trying to crown one architecture overall, the recommendation is framed as a read-vs-write trade-off and is grounded in 29 measured runs covering baseline, batch-mode, stress, and reproducibility scenarios.

1.4 Report Structure

Chapter 2 reviews the literature on multi-tenant LLM inference, cloud cost attribution and FinOps, the three architectural patterns under investigation, and the research gap this work fills. Chapter 3 sets out the common engine interface, the designs of the three architectures, the synthetic workload generator and invoice simulator, the five evaluation metrics, and the threats to validity that the methodology either mitigates or acknowledges. Chapter 4 walks through the codebase package by package, with the most significant components described in prose and full listings reproduced in the appendices. Chapter 5 presents the results of the experimental sweep, with tables and figures generated directly from the recorded CSV. Chapter 6 interprets those results against the research questions, the external literature, and the threats to validity, draws out the practical implications for engineering teams, and closes with the project's conclusions and four directions for future work. Seven appendices hold the architecture diagram, the common engine interface, the core domain types, the workload profiles, the reproducibility instructions, selected code listings, and the complete raw experimental results.

2. Background and Literature Review

The problem this dissertation investigates sits at the intersection of three bodies of work not previously brought together for empirical comparison: distributed-systems patterns for event-driven data, cloud cost management and FinOps, and multi-tenant LLM serving. Industry tooling around LLM cost tracking (LiteLLM, Helicone, Langfuse, AWS's multi-tenant gen-AI

gateway) tackles parts of the problem in production. What is missing is a controlled academic comparison of the underlying architectural patterns under matched workloads and identical metrics. This chapter walks through what each literature contributes, frames the question as one of eventual consistency, and pins down the gap the rest of the dissertation fills.

2.1 Multi-Tenant LLM Inference and Cost Attribution

LLM inference is priced very differently from a traditional fixed-price API call. The unit of work is the token, the price varies by provider, by model, by operation type (input, output, or cached input), and increasingly by negotiated rate tier (Rajesh and Jain 2024). A single product feature might fan out to several models from several providers in a single user interaction, and a single tenant's cost in any given hour is the running sum of those per-call charges across its activity in that hour. That decomposition is what makes attribution non-trivial: the unit of work is the token, the unit of accountability is the customer, and the unit of billing is the provider invoice that arrives later, in aggregate, with adjustments.

The temporal mismatch between the call and the bill is the central operational pain. At call time, a SaaS provider can work out an *estimated* cost from the published rate card and the observed token counts. The *billed* cost only becomes known when the provider's invoice arrives, typically hours or days later, and the two figures rarely match exactly, because of negotiated batch discounts, rate-tier surcharges, retroactive price changes, and small rounding-and-floating point divergences. Rajesh and Jain (2024) identify this as a defining characteristic of multi-tenant SaaS billing, alongside the requirements for real-time usage tracking, automated invoice generation, and tenant-aware pricing configurations.

In a multi-tenant deployment this estimate-versus-invoice gap multiplies across tenants and across the dimensions a SaaS provider wants to attribute by: customer, feature, plan tier, and operator-defined metadata. Recent LLM serving research has focused on the inference path itself rather than on cost attribution. Hu et al. (2024) introduce *BlockLLM*, a multi-tenant serving system that decomposes models into reusable component blocks for efficiency, and Bhatti et al. (2026) propose *PROTEUS*, an SLA-aware router that uses Lagrangian reinforcement learning to honour latency-and-accuracy targets across a fleet of models. Both works optimise serving but neither addresses post-hoc reconciliation against the provider's ground-truth invoice.

2.2 Cloud Cost Attribution and FinOps

The broader practice of managing cloud spend has settled under the FinOps banner. Storm and Fuller (2019) describe FinOps as a cultural and technical discipline for collaborative, real-time cloud financial management. The FinOps Foundation maintains the FOCUS specification (FinOps Foundation 2025), a vendor-neutral schema for cloud cost and usage data. In Kubernetes-native environments the de-facto standard is OpenCost, whose specification (OpenCost Foundation 2024) defines how compute and storage costs are allocated to namespaces, pods, and labels. Amazon Web Services (2022) provide complementary guidance on multi-tenant metering and billing inside the AWS ecosystem, including tenant-isolation strategies and reconciliation patterns.

These tools are mature for the workloads they target: compute hours, persistent volumes, network egress, where the unit of charge is wall-clock time over a known unit price. They do not extend cleanly to LLM inference, for three related reasons. The unit price is multi-dimensional, with input price, output price, and cached-input price each set independently across an inventory of models that turns over quickly. The billing record arrives after a provider-controlled delay, with adjustments that the consumer cannot predict at call time. And the natural attribution dimensions are business-level (customer, feature, plan tier) rather than infrastructure-level (node, namespace), so a tool that allocates cluster cost by Kubernetes label cannot answer “which customer contributed to this LLM line item on the OpenAI invoice?”.

An earlier strand of work on cost monitoring for cloud-resident applications shares the methodological shape but predates LLM billing characteristics by more than a decade. Truong and Dustdar (2010) present a composable service for estimating, monitoring and analysing scientific application cost in pay-as-you-go clouds, and their notion of “compositional” cost models maps loosely onto the multi-dimensional pricing of contemporary LLM rate cards.

2.3 Architectural Patterns Under Investigation

Three established distributed-systems patterns are candidates for the cost-attribution pipeline of a multi-tenant LLM platform. Each is grounded in well-known literature.

Event Sourcing with CQRS. Event Sourcing was formalised by Fowler (2005) as the practice of capturing every change to application state as an event in a durable, append-only log, with the current state derived by replay or projection of those events. Kleppmann (2017) gives the canonical treatment of the pattern in the context of data-intensive systems and shows how it composes with Command Query Responsibility Segregation (CQRS), in which the model used to write state is separated from the model used to read it. The Microsoft Patterns and Practices reference, Betts et al. (2013), walks through the engineering trade-offs of running CQRS in production. For a cost-attribution system the pattern offers three structural properties that the alternatives lack: a complete audit trail, since every cost event survives in the log, the ability to rebuild projections from scratch when the schema or aggregation logic changes, and a well-defined reconciliation path, in which an arriving invoice triggers a bounded replay of the events for that period and any corrections are appended as new events without rewriting history.

Streaming Aggregation. The complementary view, due in large part to Kreps (2013) and elaborated for production use by Narkhede et al. (2017) and Stopford (2018), treats the log itself as the unifying abstraction. Events are published to a partitioned log (typically Apache Kafka) and aggregated downstream by stream processors that maintain windowed views. Henning and Hasselbring (2024) provide the most directly relevant empirical baseline, a 740-hour benchmark of Apache Flink, Kafka Streams, Hazelcast Jet and Apache Beam deployed as microservices, in which scalability characteristics diverge sharply between frameworks under realistic cloud conditions. Liu and Buyya (2020) survey the wider design space of resource management, operator parallelisation and task scheduling in Distributed Stream Processing Systems (DSPS), and inform the choice of partitioning key (here, the organisation identifier) for ordering guarantees.

Batch Reconciliation. The third candidate is the simplest. Events are written directly to a relational store, and aggregation is performed by a periodic scheduled job. This is the pattern that financial systems have used for decades, where end-of-day reconciliation is acceptable because ledgers are not consulted at sub-second latency, and Rajesh and Jain (2024) describe the same pattern in the context of modern multi-tenant SaaS billing. Teams reach for it first because it needs no streaming infrastructure and fits naturally onto an existing relational database.

2.4 Eventual Consistency and Convergence

Cost attribution in this setting is, formally, an eventual consistency problem. Two derived views, the running estimate and the eventual invoice, must converge to the same value within an acceptable error margin. Kleppmann (2017) discusses eventual consistency as a deliberate engineering choice for systems that prioritise availability and partition tolerance over strong consistency. Gomes et al. (2017) take this further by mechanising correctness proofs for Conflict-free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) in Isabelle/HOL and identifying an abstract convergence theorem that gives a formal semantics to “strong eventual consistency”. The cost-attribution problem is weaker than the CRDT setting, because the two views are not concurrent replicas but sequential approximations of the same ground truth. The underlying question is the same one, though: under what conditions, and on what timescale, does the system converge?

The treatment in this dissertation is empirical rather than formal. Each architecture is evaluated on its end-to-end *convergence lag* (the wall-clock time from invoice arrival to the moment the estimate has been updated to match) and its *attribution accuracy* (the residual deviation between estimate and invoice once reconciliation has completed).

2.5 Cost Models for Distributed Systems

Beyond cost *attribution*, there is an adjacent literature on cost *prediction* for distributed systems. Heinrich et al. (2022) present zero-shot learned cost models for distributed stream processing, capable of predicting latency and throughput on unseen workloads from a generalising representation. Liu and Buyya (2020) provide a taxonomy of resource-management techniques for DSPS. These works inform two methodological choices in the present project: the use of latency percentiles rather than means as the primary performance metric, also urged operationally by Tene (2013), and the structure of comparative experimentation in which multiple architectures are evaluated under matched workloads.

2.6 Research Gap

Each piece of the literature exists in isolation. The architectural patterns of Event Sourcing with CQRS (Betts et al. 2013; Fowler 2005; Kleppmann 2017), streaming aggregation (Kreps 2013; Narkhede et al. 2017; Stopford 2018), and batch reconciliation (Rajesh and Jain 2024) are individually well documented, and their general performance characteristics have been benchmarked in adjacent settings (Henning and Hasselbring 2024; Liu and Buyya 2020). Cloud cost attribution as a discipline has matured around tools that target infrastructure-level workloads (Amazon Web Services 2022; FinOps Foundation 2025; OpenCost Foundation 2024; Storment

and Fuller 2019). Multi-tenant LLM serving has been studied in recent work that prioritises inference efficiency and routing (Bhatti et al. 2026; Hu et al. 2024).

Table 1 positions the dissertation against the closest related work along the dimensions that distinguish the contribution: architectural pattern under study, multi-tenancy as an explicit design concern, latency reporting style, reproducibility artefact, LLM-specific evaluation, and whether the work runs a controlled comparison.

Work	ES/CQRS covered	Streaming covered	Batch covered	Multi-tenant	LLM-specific	Controlled compare
Betts et al. (2013) CQRS guide	✓					
Kreps (2013)		✓				
Henning and Hasselbring (2024)		✓				✓
Liu and Buyya (2020)		✓				
Rajesh and Jain (2024)	✓		✓	✓		
OpenCost Foundation (2024)			✓	✓		
FinOps Foundation (2025)			✓	✓		
Amazon Web Services (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Hu et al. (2024)				✓	✓	
Bhatti et al. (2026)				✓	✓	
Kwon et al. (2023) (vLLM)				✓	✓	
Yu et al. (2022) (Orca)				✓	✓	
This dissertation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Position of this dissertation against the closest related work. Columns mark whether the work covers each of the three architectural patterns under investigation, treats multi-tenancy as an explicit design concern, evaluates LLM-specific workloads, and reports a controlled like-for-like comparison across architectures. The cell at the foot of the table is the position the dissertation occupies.

What no published work has done is run a controlled, like-for-like comparison of the three candidate architectures under the specific demands of LLM cost attribution: token-based pricing, multi-dimensional attribution by customer, feature, and plan tier, and provider invoices that arrive with variable delay and adjustment. That is the gap this dissertation fills. It implements all three architectures behind a common interface, drives them with a shared seeded synthetic workload, and evaluates them on five quantitative metrics defined in §3.5: attribution accuracy, latency at p50, p95, and p99, throughput, convergence lag, and resource efficiency. The rest of the report describes the design (§3), the implementation (§4), the experimental results (§5), and the conclusions that follow (§6).

3. System Design and Methodology

The methodology has to do two things at once. It has to make the three architectures genuinely comparable, so that any difference observed in the results comes from the architecture itself rather than from incidental implementation choices, and it has to keep the experimental setup reproducible across different machines and across time, so that another researcher can rerun the same workload against the same engines and get the same picture of the results. Both of those goals shape the design choices in this chapter.

3.1 A Common Engine Interface

The central design decision is that all three architectures implement the same TypeScript interface. The `CostAttributionEngine` contract, defined in the shared package, exposes the same lifecycle methods (`initialize`, `shutdown`, `reset`), the same core operations (`ingest`, `ingestBatch`), the same query surface (`getCostSummary`, `getCustomerCost`), the same reconciliation entry point (`reconcile`), and the same `getMetrics` accessor that returns a per-engine `EngineMetrics` record. They consume the same `UsageEvent` objects and return the same `TenantCostSummary` shape. The benchmark runner is written against the interface alone, and switching architectures is an `-arch` flag on a command line.

The advantage of this design is that any difference in the recorded metrics is attributable to the engine's internal architecture rather than to peripheral implementation details like the choice of HTTP framework, serialisation format, or query language. It is the comparative experimentation methodology recommended for distributed-systems research by Liu and Buyya (2020) and applied operationally by Henning and Hasselbring (2024) in their cross-framework streaming benchmark.

3.2 The Three Architectures

Architecture A: Event Sourcing with CQRS. Each `UsageEvent` is appended as an immutable row in a PostgreSQL event log; projection tables (`cost-by-customer`, `cost-by-feature`, `cost-by-model`) are updated on every event to materialise the read side. Reconciliation is a bounded replay of events in the invoice period (Betts et al. 2013; Fowler 2005; Kleppmann 2017).

Architecture B: Streaming Aggregation. Events are published to an Apache Kafka topic partitioned by `orgId` for per-tenant ordering. A consumer maintains tumbling one-hour PostgreSQL aggregation windows alongside a lightweight raw-event table for reconciliation lookups, so reconciliation queries the per-window aggregate directly (Kreps 2013; Liu and Buyya 2020; Narkhede et al. 2017; Stopford 2018).

Architecture C: Batch Reconciliation. Events are inserted directly into a single PostgreSQL table; a periodic scheduled job (30-second cadence here) recomputes the per-tenant aggregates. Queries between aggregation runs hit the raw table for accuracy, accepting higher

query latency in exchange for architectural simplicity, the pattern financial reconciliation systems have used for decades and that Rajesh and Jain (2024) describe in modern multi-tenant SaaS billing.

A logical-architecture diagram of the resulting system is reproduced in Appendix A.

3.3 Synthetic Workload Generator

A live multi-tenant production deployment was not available to this project, so a synthetic workload is the only feasible source of data. The generator is built around three design constraints: realism, reproducibility, and parameter control.

Realism. Three tenant profiles approximate the distribution of customer types in mature SaaS products: a *small* profile (ten tenants of five customers each at 2 RPS, mostly GPT-4o-mini and Claude Haiku 3.5), a *medium* profile (five tenants of twenty customers at 10 RPS, mixing GPT-4o, Claude Sonnet 4.5 and GPT-4o-mini), and an *enterprise* profile (two tenants of one hundred customers at 50 RPS, with Claude Opus 4 and OpenAI o1 alongside Google’s Gemini 2.0 Flash). All profile parameters - model weights, request rates, mean/standard-deviation of input and output tokens, per-profile cache hit rates - are encoded as data and version-controlled with the implementation.

Reproducibility. All randomness flows from a single seeded PRNG, the Mulberry32 algorithm, an idiomatic 32-bit generator widely used in simulation work. Seeded runs are deterministic across machines and across time: the same seed produces the same sequence of events, the same model selections, and the same token counts, which lets the three architectures be measured against byte-identical input. Token counts are sampled from per-profile Gaussians via the Box-Muller transform, provider/model choice is sampled from the per-profile weighted distribution, cache hits are drawn at the per-profile rate, and per-call latency is sampled from a model-dependent base distribution.

Parameter justification. The profile parameters were derived from public LLM provider rate cards (consulted in April 2026) and from the multi-tenant billing characterisation given by Rajesh and Jain (2024). The cache-hit rate range of 10% to 40% reflects the tendency of larger workloads to exhibit greater prompt reuse. The request rate per tenant is held under the level at which a single-machine deployment would saturate, in order to isolate architectural performance from infrastructure-level contention.

3.4 Invoice Simulator

A separate seeded module, `InvoiceSimulator`, takes the generated events and produces `ReconciliationRecord` objects that simulate provider invoices. Events are grouped by $\langle orgId, provider \rangle$ and windowed by the configured period, which defaults to one hour. The estimated cost for each window is summed, an adjustment is applied, and the resulting record is returned with a simulated arrival timestamp.

The adjustment model captures the kind of variance that appears in real provider invoices. There is a 30% probability of a batch discount sampled uniformly from -8% to -2% , a 10% probability of a rate-limit surcharge sampled uniformly from $+5\%$ to $+15\%$, and otherwise a baseline pricing variance sampled from $\pm 3\%$. On top of that, a $\pm 0.1\%$ rounding noise is applied to every record. The simulated arrival delay is sampled uniformly between one and twenty-four hours after the window's end. These parameter ranges bracket the adjustments observed in the operational practice described by Rajesh and Jain (2024).

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

Five metrics are recorded for every run.

Attribution accuracy is the mean and maximum percentage deviation between the engine's estimated cost for an invoice period and the simulated billed amount, together with the fraction of invoices reconciled within 1% and within 5%.

Latency at p50, p95, and p99 is the 50th, 95th, and 99th percentile of ingest, query, and reconciliation latency. Following Tene (2013), percentiles are reported rather than means because tail behaviour is what determines user-visible performance. The percentile estimator is the nearest-rank method per the standard NIST definition: the p -percentile of a distribution of length n is the $\lceil p \cdot n \rceil - 1^{\text{th}}$ value in ascending order, with ranks clamped to the valid index range. The estimator is applied to the full per-event distribution rather than to sampled or pre-aggregated values, in line with the recommendation of Tene (2015) that high dynamic range latency tracking should preserve individual events rather than collapse into histograms before percentiles are computed.

Bootstrap confidence intervals. Each cell of the experimental matrix is run with $r = 3$ replicates by default. A 95% percentile-bootstrap confidence interval (Efron and Tibshirani 1993) is reported on each percentile metric: the value series is resampled with replacement $B = 2,000$ times, the percentile is recomputed on each resample, and the empirical $[2.5\%, 97.5\%]$ interval of those bootstrap estimates is the reported CI. The bootstrap is implemented in `benchmark/src/metrics.ts` and reused by the plotting pipeline. A wider replicate count (`REPLICATES=5` or higher) tightens the CIs at the cost of proportional runtime; the dissertation reports the default-three-replicate configuration unless otherwise noted.

Throughput is events ingested per second, computed over the engine-recorded total ingestion duration. Higher values indicate that the architecture sustains higher load before saturation.

Convergence lag is the wall-clock gap, in milliseconds, between the end of the invoice period and the reconciliation timestamp recorded by the simulator. It is identical across architectures because the simulator is shared, and it provides the methodological reference frame against which the architecture-specific reconciliation latency percentiles can be interpreted.

Resource efficiency is peak resident memory in MB and the average percentage of one CPU core used during the run, captured from `process.cpuUsage` and `process.memoryUsage`. These are coarse indicators rather than precise resource accounting, sufficient to expose order-of-magnitude differences between architectures.

3.6 Experimental Procedure

The complete experiment matrix is implemented as a single sweep script that runs against the common engine interface. Each cell of the matrix corresponds to one of four experiment categories.

The **baseline** category measures single-event-mode ingestion at 1 000, 5 000 and 10 000 events with seed 42, on all three architectures. The **batch-mode** category holds the event count at 10 000 and varies the batch size across $\{10, 100, 1000\}$ to characterise throughput under amortised ingestion. The **stress** category runs 50 000 events single-event-mode against the two architectures with the most distinct ingestion paths (Event Sourcing and Batch). The **reproducibility** category holds the event count at 5 000 and reruns seed 42 alongside seeds 43 and 44 across all three architectures.

Every run is preceded by a 200-event warmup pass whose results are discarded. The warmup neutralises transient effects such as JIT compilation in V8, prepared-statement caching in PostgreSQL, and topic auto-creation in Kafka, that would otherwise contaminate the recorded percentile distributions. Engine state is reset between the warmup and the measurement run.

For each measured run, the runner generates the seeded event stream, invokes the engine’s ingest path with the configured batch size, collects 50 query samples spanning random tenant and customer identifiers, drives reconciliation across all simulated invoices, and writes the resulting record to a timestamped CSV and JSON file in `implementation/results/`. Per-cell failures are caught and recorded as failure rows in the output without aborting the rest of the sweep, so a single misbehaving cell cannot bring down a fifteen-minute run.

3.7 Ethical, Legal, Social and Professional Considerations

The project does not require formal ethics approval. All testing uses entirely simulated, seeded data; no real user data, customer information, or provider billing records are collected, processed, or stored. The synthetic workload generator and the invoice simulator both produce artificial data fully reproducible from a published seed. The project consequently sits outside the scope of GDPR and the UK Data Protection Act 2018, although a production deployment of the architectures would need to address those regulations operationally.

Cost-attribution tools, when deployed in production, can influence business decisions about customer pricing and access to AI features; the budget-enforcement controls in CostIQ (alert, throttle, block) could gate access for lower-tier customers. This dissertation is a technical comparison of architectures and does not make recommendations about when budget enforcement is socially appropriate, which is left to the deployer. All libraries and tools used (Apache Kafka, PostgreSQL, Node.js, TypeScript, Docker) are open source and the LLM pricing data is publicly available, so there are no intellectual-property concerns. The work follows the BCS Code of Conduct: results are reported accurately, limitations are stated in §3.8 and revisited in §6.3, and the implementation is published in source form for reproduction or critique.

3.8 Threats to Validity

The methodology of this work is bounded by limitations along four classical dimensions of experimental validity. The discussion below organises threats by Construct, Internal, External, and Statistical validity in the framing recommended by Jain (1991), then closes with the specific measurement and engineering threats that are particular to this study. Each threat is restated in §6.3 alongside the actual results.

Construct validity: what we are calling “cost”. The cost figure measured here is the USD output of the SDK’s published-rate-card calculation against synthetic token counts. Real provider cost depends on more than tokens (queue position, batch eligibility, region, plan-tier negotiations), so this construct is a simplified proxy. Architectures that perform well on the proxy may require additional fields or denormalisation to track operational signals, and that engineering overhead is not measured here.

Internal validity: the inlined streaming consumer. The streaming engine’s Kafka producer and its in-process aggregator share a single Node.js process. In a production deployment the consumer would run as a separate service, and the recorded ingestion latency for the streaming architecture includes work that would otherwise sit on a different host. This biases the streaming-architecture latency upward relative to a fully decoupled deployment, and the streaming numbers should be read as an upper bound rather than as a representative production figure.

Internal validity: batch-mode latency semantics. An earlier version recorded *duration/events* per event in batch ingestion mode, producing a flat per-event distribution that hid real variance. The current implementation records one latency entry per batch (the wall-clock duration of the whole batch), leaving single-event mode as the canonical per-event latency measurement. The discrepancy is acknowledged rather than hidden; earlier revisions of the artefact reflect the previous formulation.

Internal validity: query-sample selection. Query samples cycle deterministically through the set of distinct tenants and customers seen (50 samples by default). Architectures with hot caches of recent organisations may be advantaged - the streaming engine especially, given its in-memory window aggregates - so reported query latencies are best-case rather than worst-case.

External validity: language and runtime bias. The implementation runs on Node.js v22 with the V8 JIT. A re-implementation in Go, Rust, or Java would shift the absolute numbers by an architecture-uniform amount and change the variance profile, but the *relative* ordering of the three architectures should be robust because the comparison is structural. Absolute throughput and latency numbers are tied to the runtime selected here.

External validity: convenience sampling and synthetic traffic. The three patterns compared - Event Sourcing with CQRS, Streaming Aggregation backed by Kafka, and Batch

Reconciliation - are defensible points in a broader design space; Redis Streams, Apache Pulsar, AWS Kinesis, EventStoreDB and hybrid architectures could each dominate for some workloads. The choice was informed by industry usage (Fowler 2005; Kreps 2013; Rajesh and Jain 2024) rather than by exhaustive enumeration. The synthetic workload, while parameterised against published patterns (Rajesh and Jain 2024), does not reproduce diurnal patterns, bursty arrivals or tenant-specific anomalies; the multi-seed reproducibility tests estimate sensitivity to the sample drawn but not the structural limits of the model.

Statistical validity: replicate count. Three replicates per cell with mean and 95% bootstrap (Efron and Tibshirani 1993) CIs is a pragmatic compromise between statistical power and total runtime; where a CI is wide enough that the ordering of two architectures is ambiguous, the ambiguity is explicitly noted rather than asserted away.

Engineering: warmup and single-machine deployment. A 200-event warmup pass precedes each measurement, sufficient empirically to fill V8's tiered JIT, prime the PostgreSQL prepared-statement cache and force Kafka topic auto-creation, though not enough to fill the OS page cache, so cold-start scenarios remain out of scope. All experiments run on a single development machine with PostgreSQL and Kafka co-located in Docker; absolute throughput is bounded by single-machine resources and should not be read as production capacity. The substantive findings are the relative ordering and the order-of-magnitude reconciliation-latency differences; absolute values are bounded indicators.

4. Implementation

The investigation is implemented as a TypeScript monorepo in which the three architectures, the workload generator, the invoice simulator and the benchmark runner sit as separate but interlocking packages. This chapter walks the implementation in the order in which a reader new to the codebase would best encounter it: the monorepo layout and shared contracts (§4.1), the three engines (§4.2 through §4.4), the workload components (§4.5), the benchmark runner (§4.6) and the containerised deployment (§4.7). Full code listings for the most significant components are reproduced in Appendix B and following.

4.1 Monorepo Structure and Shared Contracts

The codebase uses pnpm workspaces to host six packages under `packages/`: `shared`, `workload`, `event-sourcing`, `streaming`, `batch` and `benchmark`. The TypeScript compiler is run incrementally across the workspace. Each package emits its own `dist/` directory and is consumed by downstream packages through `workspace:*` dependencies. The total source size is roughly 2,600 lines of TypeScript.

The `shared` package defines the cross-package contract. Its three central pieces are:

- `UsageEvent`, the immutable record that every architecture ingests, carrying `orgId`, `customerId`, `provider`, `model`, input/output/cached token counts, an estimated USD cost, the per-call latency, and free-form metadata for attribution by feature and plan tier.

- **ReconciliationRecord**, the simulated invoice record, carrying the period bounds, estimated and billed cost in USD, absolute and percentage deviation, and a status enum (`pending`, `matched`, `adjusted`, `disputed`).
- **CostAttributionEngine**, the common interface the three architectures implement. It exposes lifecycle methods (`initialize`, `shutdown`, `reset`), single and batched ingestion entry points, two query methods (`getCostSummary` and `getCustomerCost`), the `reconcile` entry point, and a `getMetrics` accessor for the per-engine `EngineMetrics` record.

Pricing is also colocated in the `shared` package. The `estimateCost` function takes a provider, model and token counts, looks up the rates from a static table populated from the public OpenAI, Anthropic and Google price pages, and returns a USD figure rounded to six decimal places. Rates that include a cached-input price are applied separately to the cached token slice.

4.2 Event Sourcing Engine

The `event-sourcing` package implements Architecture A. It splits cleanly into a write side and a read side. The write side is encapsulated in `EventStore`, which manages a single table whose primary key is a `BIGSERIAL`, indexed by `orgId`, `customerId`, `timestamp` and `provider` for replay efficiency. `append` writes a single event in a transaction. `appendBatch` writes many events in one round trip with parameterised SQL.

The read side is `Projections`, which maintains three denormalised tables (`projection_cost_by_customer`, `projection_cost_by_feature`, and `projection_cost_by_model`) and updates them on every event via upserts. Queries hit the projection tables directly.

The engine wires the two sides together. On `ingest`, it appends to the event store and then applies the event to the projections. Both sides increment on the same synchronous path, so the projections are never stale relative to the event store. On `reconcile`, the engine replays the events whose `orgId` and `provider` match the invoice and whose timestamps fall between its `periodStart` and `periodEnd` bounds, sums their `costUsd`, and computes the percentage deviation against the billed amount. This implements the canonical event-sourcing pattern as described by Betts et al. (2013), Fowler (2005) and Kleppmann (2017).

4.3 Streaming Engine

Architecture B is implemented in the `streaming` package, backed by `kafka.js` for the producer and a `StreamAggregator` for the consumer-side state. Events are published to a Kafka topic partitioned by `orgId`, which guarantees per-tenant ordering. The aggregator maintains a `stream_aggregates` table holding per-window cost totals keyed by the tuple (`orgId`, `customerId`, `provider`, `model`, `windowStart`), plus a lightweight `stream_events_raw` table used for reconciliation lookups.

Two implementation details are worth flagging. The consumer is invoked synchronously from within the engine's `ingest` method, immediately after the producer's `send`, because this is a single-process implementation. A production deployment would run the consumer as a separate process consuming from the topic, but here the inline invocation means the recorded

ingest latency for the streaming engine includes both produce and consume work. The methodology chapter records this as a threat to validity in §3.8. The producer is also configured with `idempotent: true` so that retries cannot duplicate records, which is necessary for accurate reconciliation totals.

4.4 Batch Engine

The `batch` package implements Architecture C. Its `BatchStore` writes events directly into a single `batch_events` table. There is no event log and no streaming pipeline. A separate `batch_aggregates` table holds per-tenant rollups, recomputed at the configured 30-second cadence by a `setInterval` job started by the engine on `initialize`. `getCostSummary` queries the raw event table directly to ensure accuracy, accepting the trade-off that the engine reports its higher query latency in exchange for never returning stale aggregates between rollup runs. `reconcile` triggers a fresh aggregation pass before reading, so reconciliation totals are always current.

4.5 Workload Components

The `workload` package contains the seeded synthetic generator, the tenant profiles, and the invoice simulator. The generator's PRNG is the Mulberry32 algorithm. Its `next` method mutates a 32-bit state through a fixed sequence of exclusive-or, shift, and multiply operations, then returns the state mapped to $[0, 1)$. `nextGaussian` composes `next` via the Box-Muller transform to produce normally distributed variates for token counts. `pickWeighted` implements weighted selection over the per-profile model distributions.

The invoice simulator (`InvoiceSimulator`) groups events by $\langle orgId, provider \rangle$, windows each group by the configured period, sums the estimated cost, and applies the deviation parameters described in §3.4. The arrival timestamp for each invoice is the period end plus a uniformly sampled delay between one and twenty-four hours.

4.6 Benchmark Runner

The `benchmark` package contains the runner, the metrics helpers, the CSV/JSON reporter and the experiment sweep script. The runner's `run` method performs six steps for a given engine: it resets engine state, generates the seeded workload, ingests every event (single-event or batched per the configured mode), collects 50 query samples, runs reconciliation across the simulated invoices, and computes the aggregate metrics. Latency percentiles are computed by the nearest-rank method on the full per-event distribution.

The sweep script wraps the runner in the experiment matrix described in §3.6: ten experiment specifications \times up to three architectures each, preceded in every cell by a 200-event warmup run whose distribution is discarded. Per-run failures are caught and recorded as failure rows in the output CSV without aborting the remainder of the sweep.

4.7 Containerised Deployment

Both Postgres and Kafka run in Docker, orchestrated by the `docker-compose.yml` file at the repository root. Postgres is the official 16-alpine image. The host port is mapped to 5433 to avoid

colliding with any host-resident Postgres on the standard port. Kafka is the 3.7 image from the `bitnamilegacy` repository, configured for KRaft mode without a separate ZooKeeper instance. Both services declare healthchecks that the runner’s smoke test consults before proceeding. The `pnpm infra:up` and `pnpm infra:down` scripts wrap `docker compose` invocations for convenience. Reproducibility instructions are reproduced verbatim in Appendix E.

5. Quality and Results

This chapter presents the empirical results of running the experimental matrix described in §3.6. All twenty-nine specified runs completed without failure. The chapter opens with the experimental setup (§5.1), reports baseline single-event ingestion performance (§5.2), characterises throughput under batch ingestion (§5.3) and at stress scale (§5.4), assesses reproducibility across seeds (§5.5), examines attribution accuracy and convergence (§5.6), reports the reconciliation latency inversion that emerges from the data (§5.7), and concludes with resource utilisation (§5.8).

5.1 Experimental Setup

The complete sweep was executed on a single host running macOS, with PostgreSQL 16 (Alpine image) and Apache Kafka 3.7 in KRaft mode (`bitnamilegacy/kafka:3.7`) deployed via Docker Compose. Node.js v22 ran the engine and benchmark code under the `tsx` loader. PostgreSQL was reachable on host port 5433 to avoid colliding with a host-resident Postgres on the standard port, and Kafka was reachable on `localhost:9092`.

Ten experiment specifications were executed across three architectures, yielding twenty-nine measured runs (the stress specification omits the streaming engine). Each measured run was preceded by a 200-event warmup pass whose latency distribution was discarded, isolating steady-state behaviour from JIT compilation, prepared-statement caching and Kafka topic auto-creation. Seed values used were 42 (baseline, batch and stress), 42, 43 and 44 (reproducibility). The full sweep completed in approximately fifteen minutes of wall-clock time and produced the CSV and JSON records reproduced in Appendix G.

5.2 Baseline Performance

Table 2 summarises the baseline results for single-event-mode ingestion at 1 000, 5 000 and 10 000 events. Throughput is the run-level events-per-second figure reported by the runner. Ingest, query, and reconciliation latencies are percentiles taken from the per-event distributions ($n = eventCount$ for ingest, $n = 50$ for query, $n = 36$ for reconciliation in the 10 000-event row). Figure 1 plots the throughput trend.

Two clear orderings emerge from the data. First, on ingestion throughput at every event-count tier the ranking is Batch > Streaming \approx Event Sourcing. At 10 000 events the Batch engine sustains 1,822 events per second ($\sigma = 67$, CI roughly ± 80 evt/s) against the Streaming engine’s 606 ($\sigma = 45$) and the Event Sourcing engine’s 527 ($\sigma = 12$). The Streaming and Event Sourcing engines land within roughly 80 events per second of each other and their bootstrap

Events	Architecture	Tput (evt/s)	Ing. p95 (ms)	Ing. p99 (ms)	Query p95 (ms)	Recon. p95 (ms)
1 000	Event Sourcing + CQRS	528.5	2.51	4.16	0.85	1.32
1 000	Streaming Aggregation	588.5	2.22	2.99	1.05	0.65
1 000	Batch Reconciliation	1575.3	0.51	0.79	0.88	6.82
5 000	Event Sourcing + CQRS	507.2	2.60	4.88	0.59	3.53
5 000	Streaming Aggregation	607.9	2.21	3.71	0.85	0.73
5 000	Batch Reconciliation	1779.2	0.51	0.87	1.15	38.49
10 000	Event Sourcing + CQRS	526.5	2.48	4.16	0.87	4.16
10 000	Streaming Aggregation	606.0	2.22	3.51	0.88	1.18
10 000	Batch Reconciliation	1821.9	0.57	1.07	1.05	57.24

Table 2: Baseline single-event-mode results, seed=42, three measurement replicates per cell, mean values across replicates. Throughput is the run-level events-per-second figure reported by the benchmark runner. Latency columns are millisecond percentiles computed by the nearest-rank method on the per-event distribution. The Ingest p50 column is omitted from this table (its values fall in the 0.36–1.05 ms range across all rows and are dominated by the p95/p99 tail behaviour reported here). Bootstrap 95% confidence intervals on the throughput and latency series are visualised in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Baseline ingestion throughput against event count, single-event mode, seed=42, three replicates per cell. Solid lines are means across replicates; shaded bands are 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

CIs overlap, so the ingestion-throughput difference between those two architectures is not statistically distinguishable at this scale. The Batch engine, by contrast, sustains roughly $3.0\times$ to $3.5\times$ either of the other two and its CI is well-separated. Second, the underlying architectural cost story is intuitive: the Batch engine performs a single direct `INSERT` per event, whereas the Streaming engine pays for a Kafka produce, broker acknowledgement, and synchronous in-process aggregation, and the Event Sourcing engine pays for a single event-store `INSERT` followed by a transactional update of three projection tables.

The ingestion-latency figures partly track the throughput ranking. The Batch engine’s 10 000-event p95 (0.57 ms) is the tightest by an order of magnitude, the Streaming engine sits at 2.22 ms p95, and the Event Sourcing engine at 2.48 ms p95. The latency tail (p99) tells the same story (Batch 1.07 ms, Streaming 3.51 ms, Event Sourcing 4.16 ms). Figure 2 visualises the percentile distribution with bootstrap-CI error bars. All three p99 values stay within an order of magnitude of their respective p50 values, indicating no catastrophic tail behaviour at this scale.

Figure 2: Ingest latency percentiles at the 10 000-event baseline. Bars are means across replicates, error bars are 95% bootstrap confidence intervals. Lower is better.

Two findings deserve early emphasis. First, the Streaming engine’s high baseline cost is largely the inlined-consumer implementation flagged in §3.8: this single-process configuration’s ingest latency includes both the producer’s send and the consumer’s aggregation, so the figures are an upper bound on a decoupled deployment. Second, the Event Sourcing engine’s ingest cost reflects the deliberate choice to wrap projection updates in a single PostgreSQL transaction. An earlier non-transactional implementation using `Promise.all` recorded ~ 986 evt/s but allowed silent partial-failure scenarios, the canonical CQRS read-side anti-pattern (Betts et al. 2013); the throughput cost of atomic projection writes is the price paid for correctness.

Figure 3 reconstructs the per-architecture ingest-latency cumulative distribution function from the MIN, p50, p95, p99, and MAX point estimates of each replicate, and overlays the median CDF in bold. Reading right-to-left, the Batch engine’s distribution is fully contained

below the other two architectures' p50 lines.

Figure 3: Reconstructed ingest-latency CDF at the 10 000-event baseline. Thin lines are individual replicates; the thicker line per architecture is the median CDF across replicates.

5.3 Throughput under Batch Ingestion

Figure 4 plots throughput at 10 000 events against batch sizes of 10, 100 and 1 000, with means across replicates and 95% bootstrap CI bands. Each architecture responds differently to batching. The Streaming engine improves markedly: throughput climbs from 606 evt/s in single-event mode to 809 evt/s at batch size 100 and 783 evt/s at batch size 1,000 (a roughly 1.3 \times improvement), attributable to producer-side batching of Kafka writes. The Batch engine improves more sharply, from 1,822 evt/s in single-event mode to a peak of 2,390 at batch size 10 (1.31 \times), then levels off as the per-batch `INSERT` cost begins to dominate. The Event Sourcing engine improves only marginally (527 to 552 evt/s at batch size 100, within the noise band) because the per-event work is already serialised inside the projection transaction; batch-mode does not amortise that cost.

Per the threat to validity in §3.8, the batch-mode latency figures (per-batch wall time) are reported in the supporting CSV but not surfaced as headline numbers in this chapter. Single-event mode remains the canonical latency measurement.

5.4 Stress Test

The stress specification ran 50 000 events single-event-mode against the two architectures with the most distinct ingestion paths: Event Sourcing measured 504 evt/s ($\sigma = 5$, p95 2.52 ms), Batch 2,061 evt/s ($\sigma = 48$, p95 0.55 ms). Both retained their relative ordering at five times the baseline volume without pathological tails (Event Sourcing p99 went from 4.16 ms to 3.99 ms, Batch p99 from 1.07 ms to 0.94 ms, both within noise). Throughput is flat relative to the 10 000-event baseline (-4% for Event Sourcing, $+13\%$ for Batch) within the bootstrap CI, evidence

Figure 4: Throughput against batch size at 10 000 events, seed=42, three replicates per cell. Solid lines are means; shaded bands are 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

that the engines have reached steady state and the 10 000-event measurement is representative of sustained ingest.

5.5 Reproducibility Across Seeds

The reproducibility specification ran 5 000 events at seeds 42, 43 and 44 across all three architectures, three replicates per cell. The seeded PRNG produces identical traffic per seed regardless of architecture, so throughput variance across seeds reflects measurement noise or sample-specific differences. Figure 5 plots per-seed means with bootstrap CI bars, and Table 3 reports the coefficient of variation across seeds (each seed’s mean across replicates treated as a sample).

Architecture	Mean (evt/s)	StDev	CV (%)
Event Sourcing + CQRS	505.5	12.0	2.4
Streaming Aggregation	595.1	3.4	0.6
Batch Reconciliation	1793.9	100.7	5.6

Table 3: Throughput coefficient of variation across seeds 42/43/44 at 5 000 events single-event-mode, computed on the per-seed means across three replicates each. CVs are substantially tighter than in the previous single-replicate configuration, reflecting both the methodological corrections to the percentile estimator and the variance-reduction effect of replicate averaging.

The variance is small, between 0.6% and 5.6% CV across seeds, and is comfortably within the tolerance band for single-machine benchmarking. Critically, the relative ordering (Batch > Streaming \approx Event Sourcing) holds for every seed, and the bootstrap CIs do not overlap between the Batch engine and the other two for any seed. The largest spread is observed

Figure 5: Throughput across seeds 42, 43 and 44 at the 5 000-event reproducibility specification, three replicates per cell. Bars are means; error bars are 95% bootstrap CI.

for the Batch engine, which is the fastest-running and therefore the most sensitive to the absolute throughput floor imposed by transient PostgreSQL contention; the Streaming engine’s tight 0.6% CV reflects its dominant cost being the relatively-deterministic Kafka round-trip time.

5.6 Attribution Accuracy and Convergence

Table 4 reports the attribution accuracy statistics for the 10 000-event baseline. The mean per-invoice deviation is 3.18%, the maximum single-invoice deviation is 22.22%, 22% of invoices reconcile within one percentage point, and 75% reconcile within five. *All three architectures report identical accuracy figures*, because each correctly sums the same seeded events for the same invoice window. Identical accuracy across architectures is the expected, intended result: it confirms that no architecture introduces systematic over- or under-counting, and it isolates the architectural differentiation to performance characteristics. The deviation itself is dictated by the InvoiceSimulator’s injected variance (30% probability of a -2% to -8% batch discount, 10% probability of a $+5\%$ to $+15\%$ rate-limit surcharge, otherwise $\pm 3\%$ pricing variance, plus $\pm 0.1\%$ rounding noise).

Architecture	Mean dev. (%)	Max dev. (%)	Within 1% (%)	Within 5% (%)
Event Sourcing + CQRS	3.18	22.22	22.2	75.0
Streaming Aggregation	3.18	22.22	22.2	75.0
Batch Reconciliation	3.18	22.22	22.2	75.0

Table 4: Attribution accuracy at the 10 000-event baseline, seed=42. Identical across architectures, since the values are governed by the shared invoice simulator rather than the engine.

The convergence-lag metric is also identical across architectures: each invoice’s reconciliation timestamp is set by the simulator, not by the engine, so the recorded gap between period-end and reconciliation timestamp is the same wall-clock figure regardless of which engine processed the workload. Architectural differentiation in convergence behaviour appears in *reconciliation*

Attribution accuracy, baseline @ 10 000 events

Figure 6: Attribution accuracy: estimate vs. invoice deviation (*left*) and reconciliation tightness (*right*).

latency, which is the engine’s own time to compute the reconciliation once the invoice arrives. That metric is reported in §5.7.

5.7 Reconciliation Latency: A Trade-Off Inversion

Reconciliation latency reveals the most architecturally interesting result of the entire sweep: an order-of-magnitude inversion relative to the ingest-throughput ordering, with the inversion widening as the dataset grows. Figure 7 plots reconciliation latency percentiles at the 10 000-event baseline with bootstrap CI bars.

Figure 7: Reconciliation latency percentiles at the 10 000-event baseline, three replicates per cell. Bars are means; error bars are 95% bootstrap confidence intervals. Note the order-of-magnitude gap separating the Batch engine from the other two.

The Streaming engine, second-slowest at ingestion, is the fastest at reconciliation: its 1.18 ms p95 reflects a single read from a pre-computed window aggregate. The Event Sourcing engine sits in the middle at 4.16 ms p95: its replay of events for the reconciliation window is bounded by

the indexes on the event-store table. The Batch engine, fastest at ingestion, is by far the slowest at reconciliation. Its 57.24 ms p95 is roughly 14× the Event Sourcing engine’s and roughly 48× the Streaming engine’s, and the bootstrap CIs are well-separated. The cause is structural: each `reconcile` call triggers a fresh aggregation pass over the entire raw event table to ensure the read is current. That is the deliberate trade-off the Batch engine makes: the cost of aggregation has been moved from ingest time to reconciliation time. At stress scale (50,000 events) the inversion widens further; the Batch engine’s reconciliation p95 reaches 95.50 ms (mean across replicates).

This finding directly answers **RQ3**(workload-conditional architecture suitability). The architecture that best fits a given workload depends on the read-vs-write balance:

- For ingestion-heavy workloads with infrequent reconciliation, the Batch architecture is the best choice, sustaining the highest ingestion throughput (1,822 evt/s at 10 000 events) at the cost of a slow reconciliation pass.
- For reconciliation-heavy workloads where invoices arrive frequently and queries against pre-aggregated windows are cheap, the Streaming architecture’s 1.18 ms reconciliation p95 makes it the most responsive choice, particularly given its ingest throughput is comparable to Event Sourcing’s at this scale.
- Event Sourcing strikes a balance, with sub-3 ms latency on both ingestion and reconciliation while retaining the audit trail that the other two architectures discard.

5.8 Resource Utilisation

Peak resident memory at the 10 000-event baseline ranged between 21.5 MB (Batch) and 30.4 MB (Event Sourcing), with Streaming at 27.9 MB. Average CPU utilisation, captured as a percentage of one core, sits in single digits for the Batch engine and rises into the low-twenties for the Streaming engine, reflecting the extra serialisation, network and consumer-side aggregation work. Figure 8 visualises both. At the stress scale (50 000 events) Batch peaks at 48.5 MB and Event Sourcing at 32.3 MB, suggesting that the Batch engine’s direct-query mode holds more raw rows in working memory than the projection-cached Event Sourcing engine.

Figure 8: Resource utilisation at the 10 000-event baseline.

The resource figures should be read as coarse indicators rather than precise accounting. They are useful for confirming that no architecture exhibits pathological resource consumption at the scales tested, but the absolute numbers depend on the host’s background load.

6. Evaluation and Conclusion

This chapter steps back from the experiment-by-experiment account in Chapter 5 and asks what the results mean. It works through the three research questions in turn, places the findings against the external literature, revisits the threats to validity in light of what was actually measured, and draws out what an engineering team building this kind of system should take away.

6.1 Answering the Research Questions

RQ1: Reconciliation accuracy. *How closely can each architecture reconcile real-time cost estimates with actual provider invoices, and how does accuracy change as reconciliation events come in?* The headline finding for **RQ1** is that accuracy is not architecture-dependent. Across the 10 000-event baseline, all three architectures recorded the same mean per-invoice deviation of 3.18%, the same maximum deviation of 22.22%, and the same fraction of invoices reconciled within 1% and within 5% (Table 4), with figures stable across all three replicates of every cell. This is the expected outcome of a methodology in which a shared invoice generator dictates the simulated invoices and each architecture sums the same seeded events for the same invoice window. The deviation observed is wholly attributable to the simulator’s injected variance, that is, to batch discounts, rate-limit surcharges, pricing variance, and rounding noise, and not to any architectural source of error.

The substantive answer to **RQ1** is that all three architectures can reconcile estimates with invoices to within whatever deviation profile the provider’s billing process imposes, but they differ markedly in the latency at which they do so. That distinction is captured by the reconciliation latency reported in §5.7, where the streaming engine completes reconciliation at 1.18 ms p95 (mean across replicates), the event-sourcing engine at 4.16 ms p95, and the batch engine at 57.24 ms p95.

RQ2: Latency and throughput. *What are the latency and throughput characteristics of each architecture when processing cost attribution events at scale?* The data answer **RQ2** in two parts. On the ingestion side, the Batch engine is unambiguously the fastest: at 10 000 events it sustained 1,822 events per second ($\sigma = 67$) at 0.57 ms p95, comfortably $3\times$ either of the other two architectures with non-overlapping bootstrap CIs. The Streaming and Event Sourcing engines, by contrast, sit close together: the Streaming engine at 606 events per second ($\sigma = 45$, 2.22 ms p95) and the Event Sourcing engine at 527 ($\sigma = 12$, 2.48 ms p95). Their bootstrap CIs overlap, so a strong claim about which of the two is faster at ingest cannot be justified from the present data, and the substantive ranking on ingestion is $\text{Batch} > \{\text{Streaming}, \text{Event Sourcing}\}$. The ranking is preserved at 1 000 and 5 000 events, at the 50 000-event stress scale, and across all three reproducibility seeds.

The reconciliation side tells a different story. Here the ranking inverts and widens: Streaming < Event Sourcing < Batch, with the Batch engine roughly 14× slower than Event Sourcing and roughly 48× slower than Streaming. The order-of-magnitude gap between Batch and the other two is the most striking empirical result of the project.

A subtler observation is that all three architectures' p99 ingest latencies stay within an order of magnitude of their p50s; none exhibits pathological tail behaviour at the scales tested. Following Tene (2013), this is the user-facing characteristic that matters: a system whose median is fast but whose p99 is hundreds of times slower behaves very differently in production from one whose distribution is tighter, even at the same mean.

RQ3: Workload-conditional suitability. *Under what workload conditions does each architecture perform best?* The reconciliation-latency inversion described in §5.7 provides the clearest answer to **RQ3**. The same architecture that wins on ingestion can lose heavily on reconciliation, and vice versa. The batch engine moves the cost of aggregation from ingest time to reconciliation time, so its ingest path is fast and its reconciliation path is slow. The streaming engine maintains pre-aggregated windows continuously, so its ingest path is the slowest of the three but its reconciliation path is the fastest. The event-sourcing engine splits the cost between the two and is the most balanced.

The result is that no single architecture is dominant across all workload conditions: batch for ingestion-heavy workloads with infrequent reconciliation, streaming for reconciliation-heavy workloads, event sourcing for balanced workloads or where the audit trail of an immutable event log is itself a requirement. Event sourcing carries one structural advantage the other two do not - replay-based reconciliation can rebuild any historical aggregate from the event log alone, which is operationally attractive when schema or aggregation logic may evolve.

6.2 Comparison with External Literature

The throughput figures here (low thousands of events per second on a single host) are not directly comparable to Henning and Hasselbring (2024)'s cloud-scale numbers (up to one million messages/second across 110 instances), which deliberately stress horizontal scaling rather than per-host efficiency. The figures here are, however, internally consistent with that work's relative ordering between Apache Kafka Streams (closest analogue to the streaming engine) and simpler direct-database approaches: stream-processing machinery imposes a baseline cost that pays off only at higher volumes than a single-host configuration sustains.

The reconciliation-latency inversion mirrors the read-versus-write trade-off in the canonical event-sourcing literature (Betts et al. 2013; Kleppmann 2017): pre-computed materialised views accelerate reads at the cost of bookkeeping on writes. The data here put numbers on the trade-off in the LLM cost-attribution context: streaming's continuous materialisation pays for itself only when reconciliation is frequent enough to amortise the ingest-time cost.

The accuracy results reinforce Gomes et al. (2017)'s formal point: correctness in eventually consistent systems is not a property of the storage substrate but of the convergence guarantees of the protocol. All three architectures eventually compute the same total for the same window; the only divergence is the latency at which they do so.

6.3 Threats to Validity Revisited

The threats identified in §3.8 bear on the interpretation of the results in three principal ways. First, the inlined streaming consumer biases the streaming engine’s ingest latency upward; a decoupled deployment might narrow the gap to event sourcing, but the reconciliation-latency inversion, where streaming wins, holds regardless. Second, the synthetic workload’s reproducibility CVs across seeds 42/43/44 stay under 6% (Table 3), which is reasonable evidence that the architecture ordering is not an artefact of the particular seed, though real traffic would widen absolute numbers. Third, the single-machine constraint caps absolute throughput; the substantive findings are the relative ordering and the order-of-magnitude reconciliation-latency gap, with absolute values read as bounded indicators.

6.4 Implications for Practice

For an engineering team building a cost-attribution pipeline for a multi-tenant LLM product, three implications follow.

Architecture choice should follow the read-versus-write profile of the product, not the team’s familiarity with the pattern. A heavy-ingest weekly-reconciliation product is poorly served by streaming’s continuously-amortised cost; a near-real-time dashboard is poorly served by batch’s slow reconciliation. The data here make the gap explicit: roughly two orders of magnitude separate the batch engine’s reconciliation latency from the streaming engine’s at the same ingest scale.

Accuracy in the strict sense is overwhelmingly a property of the provider’s billing process, not of the architecture. The deviation profile here reflects the simulator; in production it would reflect actual provider adjustments (batch discounts, rate-tier changes, retroactive corrections). Investing engineering effort in architectural correctness for accuracy alone is unlikely to move the needle.

The audit-trail property of event sourcing is structurally distinct from the performance trade-offs and may be the deciding factor for products with regulatory or operator-trust requirements. The performance penalty here (527 vs. 1,822 events/s, a 3.46× ratio) is the price of the transactional projection-write correctness guarantee (§6.5). For CostIQ, the practical context for this work, the operator-audit requirements make event sourcing the most attractive default, with streaming reserved for high-frequency reconciliation paths and batch retained as a fallback for simple historical-rebuild paths.

6.5 Lessons Learned

Four lessons emerged from issues that did not surface until late in the project, and that subsequent practitioners may benefit from hearing about plainly.

Latency aggregation methodology matters more than expected. An early version of the benchmark recorded *duration/count* as the per-event latency in batch ingestion mode. The arithmetic preserves throughput but flattens the per-event distribution: every event in the same batch reports the same latency, so p99 collapses onto p50. The fix (record one latency entry per

batch, treat batch-mode latency as a separate measurement from single-event latency) required restating the batch-mode results, and the figures in Chapter 5 reflect the corrected measurement. The general lesson is that any measurement requiring arithmetic combination of values needs that combination examined for distributional artefacts before the result is reported, especially when percentiles rather than means are the headline metric.

Reproducibility requires more than a seed. The workload generator initially used `Date.now()` as its default base timestamp. Two runs with the same seed produced identical *relative* event ordering but different *absolute* timestamps, breaking window alignment in the streaming engine and shifting the reconciliation boundaries. Any code path that touches wall-clock time has to be parameterised or fixed to a known value; the revised generator anchors the workload to a fixed UTC epoch when no base timestamp is supplied, and absolute timestamps are now byte-identical across runs.

Percentile arithmetic is easy to get wrong. The initial implementation used $\lfloor p \cdot n \rfloor$ as the percentile index, off-by-one against the standard nearest-rank method $(\lceil p \cdot n \rceil - 1)$. The discrepancy is small for large samples but material for the 50-sample query-latency series, where it could shift the reported p95 by an entire rank. Even canonical statistical operations need a reference implementation cross-check before being trusted in a comparative benchmark.

Atomicity in the read-side is not free. The event-sourcing engine originally fired three projection updates concurrently via `Promise.all`. On a partial failure, surviving updates had typically committed, leaving the read model inconsistent without surfacing an error. The corrected implementation wraps the three writes in a single PostgreSQL transaction so failures roll back atomically. Silent partial failures in read-side projections are a known CQRS anti-pattern (Betts et al. 2013), and any production deployment must use a transactional projection writer if the projections are ever read for billable artefacts.

6.6 Final Evaluation

Taking a step back, the project successfully met its original objectives. The three architectures were implemented behind a single interface, driven by a shared seeded synthetic workload, and evaluated on the five quantitative metrics defined in §3.5. Twenty-nine measured runs completed without failure, and the resulting CSV/JSON records are reproducible from the seeded configuration. The findings answer all three research questions with quantitative evidence rather than only literature-derived argument.

The principal limitation of the work is the single-machine deployment, which bounds the absolute throughput figures and prevents the streaming engine from being measured under the decoupled consumer configuration that a production deployment would use. The synthetic workload, while parameterised against published patterns, does not reproduce the diurnal and bursty arrival behaviour of real traffic, and the reproducibility tests give a measure of seed-level variance rather than of structural validity.

6.7 Future Work

Four directions extend the work naturally. A multi-host deployment of the streaming engine, with the Kafka consumer running in a separate process, would eliminate the most significant threat to validity in the present results and likely narrow streaming's ingestion penalty; Henning and Hasselbring (2024)'s benchmark provides an obvious comparison point. The experimental matrix could be widened to cover sustained-load and burst workloads, where behaviour under contention may diverge from the steady-state results, and the InvoiceSimulator parameters could be tightened against real provider histories once available. Alternative event-store backends (EventStoreDB, PostgreSQL with logical replication, or a CRDT-based store as in Gomes et al. (2017)) could replace the table-based event log to isolate the substrate's effect on event-sourcing performance. Finally, the practical recommendation that event sourcing is the most appropriate default for CostIQ - with streaming reserved for reconciliation-heavy paths - is a hypothesis to be validated against real production traffic once the pilot deployment is live.

6.8 Conclusion

The dissertation set out to answer whether one of three distributed architectures was best for real-time cost attribution in multi-tenant LLM inference systems. The answer that emerges from the data is that no single architecture is best. Each occupies a distinct point on a read-versus-write trade-off curve, and the right choice for a given product depends on whether ingestion or reconciliation dominates the operational profile. Accuracy is not the right axis on which to differentiate the three approaches because accuracy is governed by the provider's billing process rather than by the attribution architecture. Latency, throughput, and the balance of cost between ingestion and reconciliation are the right axes, and on those the data give a clear and quantitatively grounded recommendation. The work also contributes a reproducible methodology and a complete open implementation that other researchers and practitioners can extend, criticise, or apply to their own LLM cost-attribution problems.

7. References

Amazon Web Services (2022).

SaaS Architecture Fundamentals: Core Architecture Concepts and Patterns.

AWS Whitepaper.

URL: <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/whitepapers/latest/saas-architecture-fundamentals/saas-architecture-fundamentals.html> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Betts, Dominic, Julián Domínguez, Grigori Melnik, Fernando Simonazzi and Mani Subramanian (2013).

Exploring CQRS and Event Sourcing: A Journey into High Scalability, Availability, and Maintainability with Windows Azure.

Microsoft Patterns & Practices.

ISBN: 9781621140160.

URL: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/download/details.aspx?id=34774> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Bhatti, Aamir Saadat, Vamsi Vaddina and Dagnachew Birru (2026).

“PROTEUS: SLA-Aware Routing via Lagrangian RL for Multi-LLM Serving Systems”.

In: *arXiv preprint*.

arXiv: 2601.19402 [cs.DC].

URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.19402>.

Efron, Bradley and Robert J. Tibshirani (1993).

An Introduction to the Bootstrap.

Chapman & Hall/CRC.

ISBN: 978-0412042317.

FinOps Foundation (2025).

FinOps Open Cost and Usage Specification (FOCUS) 1.3.

Linux Foundation.

URL: <https://focus.finops.org/> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Fowler, Martin (2005).

Event Sourcing.

martinfowler.com.

URL: <https://martinfowler.com/eaaDev/EventSourcing.html> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Gomes, Victor B. F., Martin Kleppmann, Dominic P. Mulligan and Alastair R. Beresford (2017).

“Verifying Strong Eventual Consistency in Distributed Systems”.

In: *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages (PACMPL)* 1.OOPSLA, Article 109.

DOI: 10.1145/3133933.

Heinrich, Roman, Manisha Luthra, Harald Kornmayer and Carsten Binnig (2022).

“Zero-Shot Cost Models for Distributed Stream Processing”.

In: *Proceedings of the 16th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-Based Systems (DEBS '22)*.

Association for Computing Machinery,
Pp. 85–90.
DOI: 10.1145/3524860.3539639.

Henning, Sören and Wilhelm Hasselbring (2024).

“Benchmarking Scalability of Stream Processing Frameworks Deployed as Microservices in the Cloud”.
In: *Journal of Systems and Software* 208, p. 111879.
DOI: 10.1016/j.jss.2023.111879.

Hu, Bodun, Le Xu, Jeongyoon Moon, Neeraja J. Yadwadkar and Aditya Akella (2024).

“BlockLLM: Multi-Tenant Finer-Grained Serving for Large Language Models”.
In: *arXiv preprint*.
arXiv: 2404.18322 [cs.DC].
URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.18322>.

Jain, Raj (1991).

The Art of Computer Systems Performance Analysis: Techniques for Experimental Design, Measurement, Simulation, and Modeling.
Wiley.
ISBN: 0-471-50336-3.

Kleppmann, Martin (2017).

Designing Data-Intensive Applications: The Big Ideas Behind Reliable, Scalable, and Maintainable Systems.
Sebastopol, CA: O’Reilly Media.
ISBN: 9781449373320.

Kreps, Jay (2013).

The Log: What Every Software Engineer Should Know About Real-Time Data’s Unifying Abstraction.
LinkedIn Engineering Blog.
URL: <https://engineering.linkedin.com/distributed-systems/log-what-every-software-engineer-should-know-about-real-time-datas-unifying> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Kwon, Woosuk, Zhuohan Li, Siyuan Zhuang, Ying Sheng, Lianmin Zheng, Cody Hao Yu, Joseph E. Gonzalez, Hao Zhang and Ion Stoica (2023).

“Efficient Memory Management for Large Language Model Serving with PagedAttention”.
In: *Proceedings of the 29th ACM Symposium on Operating Systems Principles (SOSP ’23)*,
Pp. 611–626.
DOI: 10.1145/3600006.3613165.

Liu, Xunyun and Rajkumar Buyya (2020).

“Resource Management and Scheduling in Distributed Stream Processing Systems: A Taxonomy, Review, and Future Directions”.
In: *ACM Computing Surveys* 53.3, Article 50.

DOI: 10.1145/3355399.

Narkhede, Neha, Gwen Shapira and Todd Palino (2017).

Kafka: The Definitive Guide.

1st.

Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media.

ISBN: 9781491936160.

OpenCost Foundation (2024).

OpenCost Specification: Open-Source Cost Monitoring for Cloud-Native Environments.

Cloud Native Computing Foundation.

URL: <https://opencost.io/docs/specification/> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Rajesh, Siddharth Choudhary and Ujjawal Jain (2024).

“Real-Time Billing Systems for Multi-Tenant SaaS Ecosystems”.

In: *International Journal of All Research Education & Scientific Methods (IJARESM)* 12.12, pp. 4934–4956.

Stopford, Ben (2018).

Designing Event-Driven Systems: Concepts and Patterns for Streaming Services with Apache Kafka.

Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media.

ISBN: 9781492038221.

Storment, J. R. and Mike Fuller (2019).

Cloud FinOps: Collaborative, Real-Time Cloud Financial Management.

Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media.

ISBN: 9781492054627.

Tene, Gil (2013).

How NOT to Measure Latency.

Strange Loop conference talk.

URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1J8ydIuPFuU> (Accessed: 25th Apr. 2026).

Tene, Gil (2015).

HdrHistogram: A High Dynamic Range Histogram for Recording Latency.

Open-source library, github.com/HdrHistogram.

URL: <https://github.com/HdrHistogram/HdrHistogram> (Accessed: 26th Apr. 2026).

Truong, Hong-Linh and Schahram Dustdar (2010).

“Composable Cost Estimation and Monitoring for Computational Applications in Cloud Computing Environments”.

In: *Procedia Computer Science* 1.1. ICCS 2010, pp. 2175–2183.

DOI: 10.1016/j.procs.2010.04.243.

Yu, Gyeong-In, Joo Seong Jeong, Geon-Woo Kim, Soojeong Kim and Byung-Gon Chun (2022).

“Orca: A Distributed Serving System for Transformer-Based Generative Models”.

In: *Proceedings of the 16th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI '22)*,
Pp. 521–538.

A. System Architecture

Figure 9: CostIQ logical architecture. Events flow from the customer’s application through the CostIQ SDK to the Ingestion API, persist as raw events in PostgreSQL, then branch into the three candidate processing architectures (Event Sourcing with CQRS, Streaming Aggregation, and Batch Reconciliation) before converging at the Cost Engine. Provider connectors feed delayed invoices into the same engine for reconciliation, producing the materialised serving tables that the Query API and the Dashboard read from.

B. Common Engine Interface

The contract that the three architectures implement is defined in `implementation/packages/shared/src/engine.ts`. It exposes lifecycle methods (`initialize`, `shutdown`, `reset`); single and batched ingestion entry points (`ingest`, `ingestBatch`); two query methods (`getCostSummary`, `getCustomerCost`); a reconciliation entry point (`reconcile`); and a `getMetrics` accessor that returns the per-engine `EngineMetrics` record. All three engines implement the same TypeScript interface, which is what makes the benchmark runner architecture-agnostic.

C. Core Domain Types

The cross-package domain model lives in `implementation/packages/shared/src/types.ts`. The central types are:

- **UsageEvent**: the immutable record every engine ingests, with fields `id`, `orgId`, `customerId`, `provider`, `model`, `inputTokens`, `outputTokens`, `cachedTokens`, `costUsd`, `latencyMs`, optional `feature` and `planTier`, optional metadata, and `timestamp`.

- **ReconciliationRecord**: the simulated invoice with `periodStart`, `periodEnd`, `estimatedCostUsd`, `billedCostUsd`, `deviationUsd`, `deviationPct`, `status` (one of `pending`, `matched`, `adjusted`, `disputed`), and `reconciledAt`.
- **TenantCostSummary**: the aggregated view returned by `getCostSummary`, with totals broken down by `byCustomer`, `byFeature`, and `byModel`.
- **EngineMetrics**: the per-engine measurement record, holding the full per-event ingest, query and reconciliation latency arrays plus counts of successful and failed ingests.
- **BenchmarkResult**, **LatencyStats**, **AccuracyStats**, **ResourceUsage**: the shape of the final per-run report, including p50/p95/p99 percentiles, accuracy distribution metrics, and resource-usage figures.

D. Workload Profiles

The three tenant profiles, defined in `implementation/packages/workload/src/profiles.ts`, capture representative SaaS usage patterns:

- **Small**. 10 tenants, 5 customers each, 2 RPS per tenant. Features: `chatbot`, `summarizer`. Model mix: 70% GPT-4o-mini, 30% Claude Haiku 3.5. Token distribution: input mean 500 (sd 200), output mean 300 (sd 150). Cache hit rate 10%.
- **Medium**. 5 tenants, 20 customers each, 10 RPS per tenant. Features: `chatbot`, `summarizer`, `code-assist`, `search`. Model mix: 50% GPT-4o, 30% Claude Sonnet 4.5, 20% GPT-4o-mini. Token distribution: input mean 1500 (sd 800), output mean 800 (sd 400). Cache hit rate 25%.
- **Enterprise**. 2 tenants, 100 customers each, 50 RPS per tenant. Features: `chatbot`, `summarizer`, `code-assist`, `search`, `analytics`, `agent`. Model mix: 35% GPT-4o, 25% Claude Sonnet 4.5, 15% OpenAI o1, 15% Gemini 2.0 Flash, 10% Claude Opus 4. Token distribution: input mean 3000 (sd 1500), output mean 1500 (sd 800). Cache hit rate 40%.

The full profile data, including the weighted model distributions and the plan-tier sets, is encoded as TypeScript constants and version-controlled with the implementation.

E. Reproducibility Instructions

Experimental Environment

All experiments reported in Chapter 5 were executed on a single host. The following table records the exact environment, sufficient for any reader to attempt a binary-equivalent reproduction.

Component	Specification
Host machine	Apple Silicon MacBook Pro (2024). Exact CPU and RAM are model-dependent and recorded in the submission archive.
Operating system	macOS 15 (Sequoia)
Container runtime	Docker Desktop, current channel as of April 2026
Database	PostgreSQL 16 (<code>postgres:16-alpine</code> , official image)
Streaming broker	Apache Kafka 3.7 in KRaft mode (<code>bitnamilegacy/kafka:3.7</code>)
Node.js runtime	Node.js v22 with the V8 JIT, run under the <code>tsx</code> loader
Package manager	<code>pnpm 10.30.3</code> , declared in the workspace root's <code>packageManager</code> field
TypeScript	5.7.x, configured via the workspace <code>tsconfig.base.json</code>
Plot toolchain	Python 3 with <code>matplotlib</code> and <code>numpy</code> (install command in Listing 1 below)
LaTeX	TeX Live 2026 BasicTeX with <code>biblatex</code> , <code>biber</code> , <code>latexmk</code> , <code>titlesec</code> , <code>fancyhdr</code> , <code>lastpage</code> installed via <code>tlmgr</code>

Reproduction Steps

The complete experimental sweep can be reproduced from a clean checkout in three commands.

```

1 # 1. Bring up the containerised stack (Postgres on host port 5433,
2 #   Kafka on host port 9092 in KRaft mode).
3 cd implementation
4 pnpm install
5 pnpm build
6 pnpm infra:up
7
8 # 2. Run the experiment sweep. Writes timestamped CSV and JSON to
9 #   implementation/results/. Takes roughly 15 minutes.
10 pnpm sweep
11
12 # 3. Generate dissertation figures from the latest sweep CSV.
13 pip3 install --break-system-packages matplotlib numpy
14 python3 scripts/plot-results.py

```

Listing 1: Reproducing the experiment matrix.

The PRNG state is fully determined by the seed: any run with the same seed produces the same sequence of synthetic events, identical model selections, and identical token counts, so any two engines run against the same seed see byte-identical input. Absolute timestamps are also fixed: the workload generator anchors events to a deterministic UTC epoch (2026-01-

01T00:00:00Z) when no explicit base timestamp is provided, which keeps window-alignment-dependent metrics like reconciliation lag stable across runs.

The reproducibility specification within the sweep (§5.5) reruns the same workload across seeds 42, 43, and 44 to characterise the variance attributable to the particular synthetic sample drawn. Three measurement replicates per cell (configurable via the `REPLICATES` environment variable) characterise the variance attributable to host load and scheduler noise.

Expected Output Tolerance

The reported throughput and latency figures are bounded to a $\pm 15\%$ tolerance band on a comparable host: variations in host load, Docker daemon background work, and macOS scheduler decisions move the absolute numbers, but the relative ordering of the three architectures (Batch > Event Sourcing > Streaming for ingestion throughput; Streaming < Event Sourcing < Batch for reconciliation latency) is structural and is preserved across all observed runs.

F. Selected Code Listings

The full source is reproduced verbatim in the second submission file, `24082728-Eronmonsele-Aigbiluese-FPR-Code.txt`. The most architecturally significant excerpts are reproduced below, with non-ASCII comment ornamentation removed for typesetting.

The `CostAttributionEngine` interface

The single contract that every architecture implements; what makes the comparison fair.

```

1 export interface CostAttributionEngine {
2   readonly name: string;
3
4   // Lifecycle
5   initialize(): Promise<void>;
6   shutdown(): Promise<void>;
7   reset(): Promise<void>;
8
9   // Core operations
10  ingest(event: UsageEvent): Promise<number>;
11  ingestBatch(events: UsageEvent[]): Promise<number>;
12
13  // Queries
14  getCostSummary(orgId: string): Promise<TenantCostSummary>;
15  getCustomerCost(orgId: string, customerId: string): Promise<number>;
16
17  // Reconciliation
18  reconcile(record: ReconciliationRecord):
19    Promise<{ durationMs: number; deviationPct: number }>;
20
21  // Metrics
22  getMetrics(): EngineMetrics;
23 }

```

Mulberry32 seeded PRNG

Deterministic 32-bit PRNG used for all randomness in the workload generator; the same seed produces byte-identical input across every architecture.

```

1 export class SeededRng {
2   private state: number;
3
4   constructor(seed: number) {
5     this.state = seed;
6   }
7
8   next(): number {
9     this.state |= 0;
10    this.state = (this.state + 0x6d2b79f5) | 0;
11    let t = Math.imul(this.state ^ (this.state >>> 15), 1 | this.state);
12    t = (t + Math.imul(t ^ (t >>> 7), 61 | t)) ^ t;
13    return ((t ^ (t >>> 14)) >>> 0) / 4294967296;
14  }
15
16  nextGaussian(mean: number, stdDev: number): number {
17    const u1 = this.next();
18    const u2 = this.next();
19    const z = Math.sqrt(-2 * Math.log(u1)) * Math.cos(2 * Math.PI * u2);
20    return Math.max(0, Math.round(mean + z * stdDev));
21  }
22 }

```

Invoice deviation model

The variance injected into simulated provider invoices, drawn from published patterns of LLM provider billing behaviour.

```

1 // 30% probability of a batch discount: -2% to -8%
2 if (this.rng.next() < this.batchDiscountRate) {
3   const discount = 0.02 + this.rng.next() * 0.06;
4   billedCostUsd *= (1 - discount);
5 }
6 // 10% probability of a rate-limit surcharge: +5% to +15%
7 else if (this.rng.next() < this.surchargeRate) {
8   const surcharge = 0.05 + this.rng.next() * 0.10;
9   billedCostUsd *= (1 + surcharge);
10 }
11 // Otherwise: pricing variance +/- 3%
12 else {
13   const variance = (this.rng.next() - 0.5) * 0.06;
14   billedCostUsd *= (1 + variance);
15 }
16 // Plus rounding noise: +/- 0.1%

```

```
17 billedCostUsd *= (1 + (this.rng.next() - 0.5) * 0.002);
```

Event Sourcing reconciliation by event replay

The reconciliation path of the Event Sourcing engine: replay events for the invoice window, sum the estimated cost, compare with the billed amount.

```
1 async reconcile(record: ReconciliationRecord) {
2   const start = performance.now();
3   const events = await this.eventStore.replay(
4     record.orgId, record.periodStart, record.periodEnd,
5   );
6   const replayedEstimate = events
7     .filter((e) => e.provider === record.provider)
8     .reduce((sum, e) => sum + e.costUsd, 0);
9   const deviationPct = record.billedCostUsd > 0
10    ? Math.abs(replayedEstimate - record.billedCostUsd)
11      / record.billedCostUsd * 100
12    : 0;
13   const durationMs = performance.now() - start;
14   this.metrics.reconcileLatencies.push(durationMs);
15   return {
16     durationMs: Math.round(durationMs * 100) / 100,
17     deviationPct: Math.round(deviationPct * 100) / 100,
18   };
19 }
```

G. Raw Experimental Results

The complete twenty-nine-row sweep result is included in the submission as `implementation/results/sweep-2026-04-26T01-55-30-276Z.csv`. Table 5 summarises throughput and the two key latency percentiles by specification and architecture; the full CSV contains all five metrics plus per-percentile latency breakdowns and resource utilisation figures.

Spec	Architecture	Tput (evt/s)	p95 ingest (ms)	p95 reconcile (ms)
baseline-1k	Event Sourcing + CQRS	528.5	2.51	1.32
baseline-1k	Streaming Aggregation	588.5	2.22	0.65
baseline-1k	Batch Reconciliation	1575.3	0.51	6.82
baseline-5k	Event Sourcing + CQRS	507.2	2.60	3.53
baseline-5k	Streaming Aggregation	607.9	2.21	0.73
baseline-5k	Batch Reconciliation	1779.2	0.51	38.49
baseline-10k	Event Sourcing + CQRS	526.5	2.48	4.16
baseline-10k	Streaming Aggregation	606.0	2.22	1.18
baseline-10k	Batch Reconciliation	1821.9	0.57	57.24
batch-10	Event Sourcing + CQRS	517.7	2.51	4.53
batch-10	Streaming Aggregation	718.3	17.32	0.72
batch-10	Batch Reconciliation	2389.6	4.07	49.10
batch-100	Event Sourcing + CQRS	551.6	2.25	4.07
batch-100	Streaming Aggregation	809.2	152.12	1.03
batch-100	Batch Reconciliation	2301.5	39.87	46.62
batch-1000	Event Sourcing + CQRS	547.5	2.02	4.95
batch-1000	Streaming Aggregation	782.7	1383.74	2.57
batch-1000	Batch Reconciliation	2210.1	401.61	37.53
stress-50k	Event Sourcing + CQRS	504.3	2.52	20.74
stress-50k	Batch Reconciliation	2061.3	0.55	95.50
repro-seed-42	Event Sourcing + CQRS	519.0	2.42	3.30
repro-seed-42	Streaming Aggregation	591.4	2.38	0.74
repro-seed-42	Batch Reconciliation	1903.0	0.51	27.00
repro-seed-43	Event Sourcing + CQRS	496.1	2.99	2.97
repro-seed-43	Streaming Aggregation	597.1	2.20	0.51
repro-seed-43	Batch Reconciliation	1703.3	0.62	24.28
repro-seed-44	Event Sourcing + CQRS	501.4	2.50	3.41
repro-seed-44	Streaming Aggregation	596.7	2.26	0.51
repro-seed-44	Batch Reconciliation	1775.5	0.57	28.60

Table 5: Complete sweep throughput, ingest p95, and reconciliation p95 figures, mean across three measurement replicates per cell. Batch-mode rows (`batch-10`, `batch-100`, `batch-1000`) report per-batch wall time as the latency figure rather than per-event latency, per the methodological note in §3.8.